

MOLECULAR TECHNIQUES USED FOR IDENTIFYING FISH-A REVIEW

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ABSTRACTS

Species identification is a fundamental part of recognizing and describing biodiversity. The difficulty in assigning an organism to a biologically meaningful category should be well considered before the use of any molecular identification tool. Molecular methods or tools provide valuable data on species diversity through their ability to detect variation at the DNA level. These methods are based on the assumption that individuals from a same species carry specific DNA (or protein) sequences that are different from those found in individuals from other species. Traditionally fish species identification is based on external morphological and meristic features. But in most cases morphological and meristic features are of limited value for identification and differentiation purposes, even with whole specimens, because they can show either considerable intraspecific variations or small differences between species. DNA-based identification methods offer an analytically powerful addition or even an alternative. Here we briefly review modern technological achievements for DNA analysis that offer great potentials for the identification of fish species.

KEYWORDS: RFLP, RAPD, AFLPs, Conventional PCR, SSCP and PCR cloning and sequencing

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INTRODUCTION

Species identification is a fundamental part of recognizing and describing biodiversity. Traditionally, identification has been based on morphological diagnoses provided by taxonomic studies (Jinbo *et al.*, 2011). The concept of “species” is perhaps the most debated subject in evolutionary biology as demonstrated by the existence of more than twenty definitions founded on different methods and criteria (Hey 2001). The difficulty in assigning an organism to a biologically meaningful category should be well considered before the use of any molecular identification tool. Researchers should be aware of the evolutionary history and taxonomic position of the specimen under study. Ideally, they should understand the order of branching and ages of divergence (phylogeny) of the organisms in examination and be familiarized with the nomenclature used in previous studies (Pereira *et al.*, 2008).

Molecular methods or tools provide valuable data on species diversity through their ability to detect variation at the DNA level. These methods are based on the assumption that individuals from a same species carry specific DNA (or protein) sequences that are different from those found in individuals from other species. However, the distribution of a given molecular variant in time and in space will be influenced by the reproductive success of individuals, migratory events and random genetic drift. Therefore, it should be realized that a continuous genetic

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variability does exist among individuals of a species. The level of intraspecies diversity in the locus under study has to be properly assessed before undertaking any taxonomic identification in order to guarantee that there is no overlap between intraspecies variation and interspecies divergence. Furthermore, different loci have variable rates of evolution owing to the action of processes such as mutation and recombination (Sunnucks, 2000). Therefore, to choose the appropriate loci is vital to the success of the identification.

A number of different techniques are available for identifying genetic differences between organisms and it is also important to keep in mind that there is no perfect DNA-typing method. The choice of technique for any one specific use will depend upon the material being studied, the resources of the laboratory, financial constraints, available expertise, time limitations and more importantly the nature of the questions being addressed (Somasundaram and Kalaiselvam). All points should be scrutinized carefully to avoid an inappropriate choice.

Molecular techniques differ in the way they sample within the genome and in the type of data that they generate. If a new method or genetic marker will be employed for the first time, the genetic composition of all species of that taxon should be determined. If possible, a representative sample of individuals should be genotyped, preferentially from different geographic locations (or from different hosts, in cases of internal parasites). The preservation of voucher specimens to serve as a future reference is also highly recommended (Pereira *et al.*, 2008).

In this review we are focusing some of the classical DNA based methods for the detection and identification of fish species and also highlight modern technologies for the screening of DNA and speculate on their potential application in the field of fish species identification.

Conventional methods for fish identification

Traditionally fish species identification is based on external morphological and meristic features. The term “morphology” is used in biology to refer to the form and structure of an organism as a whole or its component parts (body shape, pattern of colors, scale size and count, number and relative position of fins, number and type of fin rays, or various relative measurements of body parts) (Strauss and Bond 1990). It is unquestionable that the use of external or internal features of an individual is still the most applied process in both identification and taxonomy. Occasionally, the identification procedure is supported by behavioural characteristics (difference in habitat preferences, breeding seasons, epidemiology, etc) or physiological features (growth rates, biochemical composition, etc). But in most cases morphological features are of limited value for identification and differentiation purposes, even with whole specimens, because they can show either considerable intraspecific variations or small differences between species. Besides, once most morphological features have been removed during either digestion (e.g., in stomach contents) or various processing (e.g., canning, filleting), the identification becomes difficult or even impossible. Furthermore, the identification of early life stages (egg and larvae) is even more complicated than adult identification (Strauss and Bond 1990). Taken all together, these difficulties explained why researchers have attempted to develop new methods for identifying fish species without relying on morphological features.

Molecular methods for species identification

It was only in the second half of 20th century that, with the convergence of new ideas from genetics and biochemistry and a set of new technological developments, the field of species identification started to rely on information from the molecular components of cell. The first molecular methods successfully employed were based chiefly on the separation and characterization of specific proteins using electrophoretic techniques, such as isoelectric focusing (IEF) (Rehbein 1990) and capillary electrophoresis (CE) (Kvasnic̣ka 2005), high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) (Hubalkova *et al.* 2007), or immunoassay systems, such as Enzyme- Linked Immuno Sorbent Assay (ELISA) (Asensio *et al.* 2008) (for a complete review see e.g., Mackie *et al.* 1999; Civera 2003; Moretti *et al.* 2003; Hubalkova *et al.* 2007). Nowadays, different companies commercialize ELISA diagnostic kits for various applications, such as the authentication of species in milk and

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cheese (Asensio *et al.* 2008). However, for fish species identification, no immunological test kit has yet been commercialized, probably because of the potentially large number of species that might be involved (Mackie *et al.*,1999). Although each method has its own advantages, but a number of features are known to limit the use of proteins: its rapid degradation in samples under stress conditions, the risk of cross-reactions with proteins from closely related species, the differential expression of proteins in specific tissues, the scarcity of available antibodies for immunological reactions, among others (Manus *et al.*1996., Ahmed.2002). Besides, because most proteins are heat labile, they become irreversibly denatured when the flesh is cooked (e.g., in food products) and thus can no longer be examined by techniques suitable for their native states. It is, however, possible to solubilise some heat-denatured proteins in denaturing solvents such as 2% sodium dodecylsulphate or 8 M urea to obtain species-specific profiles on electrophoresis (Etienne *et al.* 2000). Antibodies used in immunoassay systems are also normally raised against undenatured proteins and thus useful for fresh samples only; even though some antibodies were developed against thermostable proteins (Ansfield *et al.* 2000). This results in that attention has now turned to DNA as a source of information. As an alternative to protein analysis, DNA-based identification methods have been developed, chiefly in the past decade (Teletchea. 2009).

There are three major characteristic of the DNA molecule over proteins makes it an extremely useful tool for molecular species identification.

1. DNA is an extremely stable and long-lived biological molecule that can be recovered from biological material that has been under stress conditions (processed food products, coprolites, mummified plant tissues, blood stains, etc). A variety of methods have also been developed to make the collection and storage of DNA samples very simple and efficient (Nsubuga *et al.*2004., Smith *et al.*2004., Rogers *et al.*, 2007).
2. DNA is found in all biological tissues or fluids with nucleated cells (or non-nucleated cells with plastids and/or mitochondria), enabling its analysis from almost all kinds of biological substrates (saliva, faeces, plant seeds, milk, etc).
3. DNA can provide more information than proteins due to the degeneracy of the genetic code and the presence of large non-coding stretches.

This results in that the tremendous advances in molecular biology, driven by the clinical arena, have now rendered possible the identification of any species in virtually any kind of organic substrate, such as muscle, fin, or blood (Lockley and Bardsley 2000; Teletchea. 2009).

Restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP)

All organisms have numerous differences in their genomic DNA sequence and therefore are genotypically distinct. The RFLP analysis is widely used for the detection of interspecies variation at the DNA sequence level. It consists the generation of species-specific band profiles through the digestion of DNA with one or more restriction endonucleases .The generated fragments are then separated by conventional agarose gel electrophoresis (Fig:1). The distinctive RFLP profile of each species is the result of the unique genomic distribution of recognition sites (generated or removed by single-base substitutions) and the distance between them (that varies due to large genomic rearrangements, such as translocations, transposable elements or tandem duplications).

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Fig. 1: Schematic representation of the Restriction Fragment Length Polymorphisms (RFLPs) method. Genomic DNA is digested by restriction enzymes, originating a set of fragments with different lengths. Species (A, B and C) are identified by running the restriction fragments on a conventional electrophoretic gel (Pereira *et al.*,2008).

This method is simple; do not require any sophisticated equipment and no prior sequence information about the species. Besides, a single pair of primers can produce a fragment that can be used for the identification of multiple species with judicious choice of restriction enzymes. However, it was only with the advent of the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) technique that RFLP analysis (known as PCR-RFLP) has become routinely used for species detection.

The main disadvantages are that incomplete digestion may occasionally occur and intraspecific variations could delete or create additional restriction sites (Lockley and Bardsley 2000). Besides, its dependence on restriction enzymes requires previous knowledge of the sample analyzed. Lin and Hwang (2007) used this technique to identify eight species of scombroids. Two sets of primers were designed to amplify 126 and 146 bp of the mitochondrial cytochrome b gene, and five restriction enzymes were determined to analyze the short length fragments. The method was successfully applied to the authentication of species in 18 commercial canned tuna

Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA (RAPD)

RAPD profiles are generated by the random PCR amplification of DNA segments using short primers of arbitrary nucleotide sequence of usually 9 or 10 nucleotides long (Williams *et al.*,1990), thus one can expect to scan the genome more randomly than using conventional techniques. These primers hybridize with sufficient affinity to different genomic regions at low annealing temperatures. Amplification products are generated when two RAPD primers anneal within a few thousand bases of each other in the proper orientation (Fig.1). Each species is identified by a specific banding pattern in an electrophoretic gel or similar technique resulting from the different genomic location of primer-binding sites (Williams *et al.*1990). This technology is also known as arbitrarily primed-polymerase chain reaction (APPCR) and has been successfully used in a number of studies (eg: Lee *et al.*1994., Lehmann *et al.* 1992., Partis *et al.*1996., Salem *et al.* 2007).

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Fig.1: Schematic representation of the Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA (RAPD) method. Species (A, B and C) are differentiated by the annealing of a single primer of arbitrary nucleotide sequence to different genomic regions. The amplified segments of DNA are separated and visualized in a conventional electrophoretic gel (Pereira *et al.*, 2008).

The important point is the banding pattern seen, when the products of PCR with random primers are electrophoresed in a reflection of the overall structure of the DNA molecule used as the template. If the starting material is total cell DNA then the banding pattern represents the organization of the cell's genome. Differences between the genomes of two organisms can be measured with RAPD. Two closely related organisms would be expected to yield more similar banding patterns than two organisms that are distant in evolutionary terms (Miesfeld, 1999).

The two main advantages of using RAPD are (a) it does not require previous knowledge of DNA sequences (but are extremely dependent on variations in laboratorial conditions such as template DNA concentration, PCR and electrophoretic settings, etc) and (b) it targets many sequences in the DNA of the sample, producing DNA patterns that allow comparison of many loci simultaneously. Besides, because of its simplicity and speed in execution, the RAPD procedure is very effective. (Lakra *et al.*, 2007) developed a PCR-RAPD method to detect interspecific genetic variability and genetic relatedness among five Indian scianids. Among the 50 arbitrary primers tested, eight were selected on the basis of reproducibility and resolution of banding patterns in all five species. The eight primers amplified a total of 85 loci in the size range from 40 to 4,697 bp. The number of stable and clear RAPD bands generated per primers varied between 9 and 12.

However, RAPD analysis presents some major disadvantages: (a) it may not be practical to identify the species of origin in products containing mixtures of species, and (b) it is not adequate for analysis of severely degraded material, because it is highly susceptible to slight changes in target-DNA quality and quantity.

Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphisms (AFLPs)

This technique is based on the selective PCR amplification of restriction fragments from a total digest of genomic DNA (Vos *et al.*, 1995). AFLP uses restriction enzymes to cut genomic DNA, followed by ligation of adaptors to the sticky ends of the restriction fragments. A subset of the restriction fragments are then amplified using primers complementary to the adaptor and part of the restriction site fragments. After final amplification, selectively amplified fragments are separated by gel electrophoresis and visualized either through autoradiography or fluorescence technologies (fig. 1). AFLP combines the advantages of RAPD and RFLP, and

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thus higher reproducibility, resolution, and sensitivity at the whole genome level compared to these two techniques.

AFLP analysis is able to detect high levels of polymorphism and has high repeatability and speed of analysis. These markers have a very high diversity index, resulting in a limited number of primer combinations required to screen a whole genome and has been applied to develop a system for the fingerprinting of an organism (Faccioli *et al.*, 1999) and for map expansion (Castiglioni *et al.*, 1998).

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of the Amplified Fragment Length Polymorphisms (AFLPs) method. Genomic DNA is digested by restriction enzymes (1) and adapters are ligated to the restriction fragments (2). By using primers with selective nucleotides at the 3'-end, only a subset of the ligated fragments is amplified (3). Species (A and B) are identified by running the amplified products on a conventional electrophoretic gel (4) (Pereira *et al.*, 2008).

This technique has been used chiefly in population genetics to determine slight differences within populations, but barely for fish species identification. Maldini *et al.* (2006) assessed the potential use of the AFLP technology to determine fish and seafood species (molluscs and crustaceans) in processed commercial products and domestic stocks. The ten primer combinations produced fragments in the size range 70–600 bp. The total number of fragments varied between 14 and 90, and major differences were observed in different systematic groups. The comparison of informative markers between unknown frozen and fresh products and references samples enabled the accurate identification of 32 different species, 20 freshwater and marine fish, four crustaceans and eight molluscs. The taxonomic characterization was performed either at the species or at the population level depending on the number of available individuals.

The AFLP technique permits the simultaneous screening of different loci randomly distributed throughout the genome. However, it is technically demanding in the laboratory, labour consuming and the interpretation of results may need automated computer analysis. Additionally, the AFLP method can be a costly technique since it requires an expensive software package to analyze a large number of AFLP patterns.

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Conventional PCR

In recent years, a number of approaches based on conventional PCR techniques have been described as a tool for species identification. Usually, a conventional PCR-based method consists in the design of PCR primers that will only originate an amplification product in the presence of DNA from the target species. The process of designing species-specific primers is now straight forward due to the vast number of genomic sequences available and software programs that assists in primer designing.

A drawback of this technique is that it does not provide information about the presence of biological material from species that are not the target of the primers. A positive result may give an idea about the presence of a particular species, but a negative result gives no information about the origin of the sample (except that it does not belong to the species for which the assay has been designed for). To avoid this problem, prior sequence knowledge is necessary to derive specific primers for all species suspected to be present in the sample. An additional disadvantage is the need of performing an electrophoresis after the PCR to verify the amplification success of expected target sequences.

The specificity and sensitivity of this kind of approach can be enhanced by performing a nested PCR, in which the target region is first amplified with an outer primer pair followed by a second amplification using an internal primer pair. Applying two rounds of PCR markedly enhances the specificity of PCR analysis because the inner primers only anneal if the proper template has been amplified with the outer primers. The chance of amplifying unspecific genomic regions is reduced with nested PCR as compared to conventional PCR since undesired sequences amplified in the first round of PCR are not likely to contain a sequence to which the primers for the second amplification reaction will bind. The possibility of carryover contamination represents a significant problem with the classical nested PCR approach since the tubes from the first amplification reaction must be opened to remove an aliquot for the second round of PCR. A number of single-tube nested PCR methods have been developed in order to overcome this problem. An additional drawback is the cost involved in doing two rounds of PCRs (Pereira *et al.*,2008).

Real-time PCR

This method is also known as quantitative PCR or Real-time quantitative PCR, or qPCR. The basic goal of real-time PCR is the detection of a specific DNA sequence in a sample by measuring the accumulation of amplified products during the PCR using fluorescent technology, a fluorescent reporter molecule is included in the assay mix and this enables the products of the PCR reaction to be measured after each cycle once a threshold has been passed. This reporter molecule is an oligonucleotide that has a fluorescent dye attached to the 5' end and a fluorescence quencher attached to the 3' end and is designed to anneal to a position between the two primers. During amplification, the 5'-3' exonuclease activity of the Taq polymerase digests the probe and releases the reporter molecule that then fluoresces. The amount of fluorescence produced is proportional to the amount of amplicon produced during PCR. An important benefit of this method is the capability to quantify the starting amount of a specific DNA sequence in the sample. DNA quantification is based on the threshold cycle (Ct), which is the cycle at which the fluorescence is detected at a predetermined value above the background. In practice, a Ct value is determined for both a normalizing target sequence that is non-discriminatory (acts as an internal standard) as well as for the specific target. To improve precision, both assays should be performed simultaneously within the same tube by using different fluorescent reporter molecules (for a complete description of qPCR techniques available see Lockley and Bardsley 2000).

The ability to monitor the progress of DNA amplification in real time depends on the chemistries and instrumentation used. Generally, chemistries consist of special fluorescent probes that must associate a fluorescent signal to the amplification of DNA. Several types of probes exist, including DNA-binding dyes like ethidium bromide, hydrolysis probes (5'-nuclease probes), hybridization probes, molecular beacons, PNA light-up probes, etc. A hydrolysis probe consists of a dual-labeled oligonucleotide with a reporter and quencher dye attached. As long as the probe is intact, no fluorescence is released by the reporter molecule when exposed to

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the appropriate wavelength of light due to the interaction with the quencher (the quencher deactivates the reporter by fluorescence resonance energy transfer). If the target of interest is present in the sample (for instance, DNA from a particular species), the probe anneals specifically between the forward and reverse primer sites during PCR. During amplification, the annealed probe is degraded by the action of DNA polymerase (5'-3' exonuclease activity) and the reporter and quencher separate, allowing the reporter's energy and fluorescent signal to be released. Either species-specific probes or primers can be used for identification of species (Monis *et al.* 2005). Molecular beacons have a similar mode of action with the reporter and the quencher hold in close proximity by a stem-loop structure (Tyagi *et al.*, 1996). When the probe hybridizes to a perfectly matched sequence, it undergoes a spontaneous conformational change (the secondary structure opens) increasing the distance between the quencher and the reporter, restoring the fluorescence.

The real-time PCR has the advantage over conventional PCR-based identification systems of working without post-PCR handling, with a minimized risk of carryover contamination in the laboratory. It also offers an increased sensitivity by permitting the discrimination of spurious PCR amplifications from non-target DNAs and is a relatively fast genotyping method, with some platforms affording highthroughput automation. Most severe disadvantages of real-time PCR methods are the incompatibility of certain platforms with some fluorescent dyes, the restricted multiplex capability and the high cost of most reagents and instrumentation.

(Casper *et al.*, 2007) experimentally compared the utility of real-time PCR for identifying consumption of captive Arctocephalus seals fed mixed prey diets (one squid and two fish taxa) with the occurrence of hard part remains of prey in scats. They found that although all test prey had robust hard parts, detecting consumption during the studied period was 1.4 and 5.8 times more likely using genetic analysis than morphological analysis of scats. However, neither DNA nor hard part methods accurately reflected the relative importance of test prey to diet using the frequency of occurrence index.

Single-Strand Conformation Polymorphism Analysis (SSCP)

This technique is based on the relationship between the electrophoretic mobility of a single stranded DNA and its folded conformations, which in turn reflects the nucleotide sequence. It's the simplest, fast and most used method of mutation detection. PCR is used to amplify the region of interest and the resultant DNA is separated as single-stranded molecules (ssDNA) by electrophoresis in a non-denaturing polyacrylamide gel (Orita *et al.*, 1989). A strand of single stranded DNA folds differently from another, if it differs by a single base, and it is believed that mutation-induced changes of tertiary structure of the DNA results in different mobilities for the two strands. These mutations are detected as the appearance of new bands on autoradiograms (radioactive detection), by silver staining of bands or the use of fluorescent PCR primers which are subsequently detected by an automated DNA sequencer (non-radioactive detection).

But this technique displays three major disadvantages: (a) the necessity to run references and samples side by side on the same gel (because SSCP profiles are highly dependent on the conditions of native PAGE), (b) intra-species variation may result in different conformations leading to wrong identification, and (c) sometimes more than two bands are visible, differing in intensity. The reason for this phenomenon may be that the ssDNA exists in several states of conformation depending on the electrophoretic conditions (Teletchea *et al.* 2009).

Weder *et al.* (2001) studied the interest of a SSCP method, originally developed to identify tuna and bonito species, for discriminating other fish and animal species. Two to four strong ssDNA bands were obtained for several fish species (e.g., blue ling, carp), while other fish species resulted in either weak (cod, spined dogfish) or no ssDNA bands (halibut, herring). They demonstrated that increasing the stringency of PCR conditions caused a more pronounced difference between strong and weak ssDNA bands. Besides, they also found that inter-laboratory reproducibility (using different chemicals, such as PCR kits, gel rehydration buffer) of the method was good (Teletchea. 2009).

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PCR cloning and sequencing

Determining the order of bases in a section of DNA is called DNA sequencing. It involves making many copies of the base sequence that match the code of a single strand of DNA. These copies vary in length by one nucleotide; the shortest is only one nucleotide long, and the longest matches the whole entire DNA strand. The sequencing option has been advocated under the name FINS: forensically informative nucleotide sequencing (Bartlett and Davidson 1992). The DNA sequence is obtained by sequencing the purified PCR fragment using the specific primers. The major advantage of this technique is that it allows detecting whether several different target DNA sequences, potentially belonging to different species, are present within the studied sample. Yet, compared to the previous molecular methods, PCR-cloning and sequencing is much more expensive and time-consuming, and explained why it has rarely been used for fish species identification. Jarman *et al.*, 2004 evaluated the interest of this technique for studying the feces of various marine predators, among which a sample of a fin whale (*Balaenoptera physalus*). They analyzed the diversity of two clone libraries containing 46 and 25 clones, which were obtained with primers designed to amplify any eukaryotic or Bilateria DNA, respectively. Therefore, they advised to use group-specific primers rather than more general or “universal” primers because it allows a considerable reduction in the diversity of PCR products to those derived from a target group of species, which can greatly simplify downstream analyses.

But now both prices and time have significantly been reduced, which explained why this method has become the preferred one. For that instances Maretto *et al.*, 2007 sequenced a 430 bp fragment of the mitochondrial 16S rRNA gene to identify four economically important species belonging to the Family Gadiformes. They identified three SNPs (single nucleotide polymorphism) that allow unambiguous discrimination between the four species. Balitzki-Korte *et al.*, 2005 used a new sequencing methodology, called pyrosequencing, which is well suited for the sequencing of short stretches located next to the sequencing primer. This technique is based on the detection of pyrophosphate (PPi) that is released from dNTPs during the DNA synthesis. Based on a cascade of enzymatic reactions, visible light is generated and detected. The amount of light is directly related to the number of incorporated nucleotides (Ronaghi 2001). Balitzki-Korte *et al.*, 2005 demonstrated that the detection by pyrosequencing of only 20 nucleotides following the sequencing primer, within a 149-bp fragment of the mitochondrial 12S rDNA gene, was sufficient to identify the biological origin of samples by alignment with a reference sequence database.

Microarray

This technique is also commonly known as DNA chip or biochip is a collection of microscopic DNA spots attached to a solid surface. Scientists use DNA microarrays to measure the expression levels of large numbers of genes simultaneously or to genotype multiple regions of a genome.

The core principle behind microarrays is hybridization between two DNA strands, the property of complementary nucleic acid sequences to specifically pair with each other by forming hydrogen bonds between complementary nucleotide base pairs. A high number of complementary base pairs in a nucleotide sequence means tighter non-covalent bonding between the two strands. After washing off non-specific bonding sequences, only strongly paired strands will remain hybridized. Fluorescently labeled target sequences that bind to a probe sequence generate a signal that depends on the hybridization conditions (such as temperature), and washing after hybridization. Total strength of the signal, from a spot (feature), depends upon the amount of target sample binding to the probes present on that spot. Microarrays use relative quantitation in which the intensity of a feature is compared to the intensity of the same feature under a different condition, and the identity of the feature is known by its position.

DNA microarrays enable the examination of complex mixtures of PCR products and, potentially, the identification of hundreds or even thousands of species simultaneously. Even though applying DNA microarrays for gene expression has already reached the routine level of high throughput systems, they have been only recently applied for the identification of species and only once for fish species during the past decade. Indeed,

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Babola *et al.* (2004) were the first to provide a microarray targeting 32 vertebrate species, including 12 mammals, 5 birds and 15 fish. Kochzius *et al.*, 2010 and Teletchea *et al.*, 2008 further explored the potential of microarray for fish species identification. Teletchea *et al.* 2008 developed a microarray-based method using cytochrome b-derived probes to identify 71 commercial and/or endangered vertebrate species in both food and forensic samples (9 birds, 34 mammals, 26 ray-finned fishes and 2 sharks). They demonstrated that this microarray-based method was relatively fast, completed within 2 days, easy to use, and that results were straightforward (high ratio between signal/ background). It was also cost-effective, particularly when compared with PCR-cloning and sequencing, and provided more accurate results. This method was successfully validated on both simple samples and mixtures (containing up to five species) as well as on fresh and degraded substrates (hair, bone, blood, muscle and foodstuffs).

Microsatellites

Microsatellites, alternatively known as simple sequence repeats (SSRs), short tandem repeats (STRs) or simple sequence length polymorphisms (SSLPs), are tandem repeats of sequence units generally less than 5 bp in length (Bruford and Wayne, 1993). These markers appear to be hypervariable, in addition to which their co-dominance and reproducibility make them ideal for genome mapping, as well as for population genetic studies (Dayanandan *et al.*, 1998). One common example of a microsatellite is a (CA)_n repeat, (Fig. 1) where n is variable between alleles.

Fig.1. Microsatellite (CA repeats) (Somasundaram and Kalaiselvam)

These markers often present high levels of inter- and intra-specific polymorphism, particularly when tandem repeats number ten or greater. CA nucleotide repeats are very frequent in human and other genomes, and present every few thousand base pairs. Inter-SSRs are a variant of the RAPD technique, although the higher annealing temperatures probably mean that they are more rigorous than RAPDs. Chloroplast microsatellites (cpSSRs) are similar to nuclear microsatellites but the repeat is usually only 1 bp, i.e. (T)_n (Provan *et al.*, 1999).

The microsatellite protocol is simple, once primers for SSRs have been designed. The first stage is a PCR, depending upon the method of detection one of the primers is fluorescently or radioactively labeled. The PCR products are separated on high resolution polyacrylamide gels, and the products detected with a fluorescence detector (e.g. automated sequencer) or an X-ray film. The investigator can determine the size of the PCR product and thus how many times the short nucleotide was repeated for each allele.

Microsatellites owe their variability to an increased rate of mutation compared to other neutral regions of DNA. These high rates of mutation can be explained most frequently by slipped strand mispairing (slippage) during DNA replication on a single DNA double helix. Mutation may also occur during recombination during meiosis. Some errors in slippage are rectified by proofreading mechanisms within the nucleus, but some mutations can escape repair. The size of the repeat unit, the number of repeats, the presence of variant repeats and the frequency of transcription in the area of the DNA repeat are the factors responsible for generating polymorphism. Larger changes in repeat number are thought to be the result of processes such as unequal

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crossing over (Strand *et al.*, 1993). Such differences are detected on polyacrylamide gels (Fig. 2.), where repeat lengths migrate different distances according to their sizes.

Fig 2: Polymorphism in microsatellites (Somasundaram and Kalaiselvam)

Over 24,000 microsatellite loci are known in teleost fishes. Majority are contributed from carps, cat fishes, perches and salmonids. Overall 40 polymorphic microsatellites DNA markers are identified for nearly 40 Indian fish and shell fish species (Ayyappan *et al.*,2011).

Denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis (DGGE)

It's the technique used for separating DNA fragments according to their mobilities under increasingly denaturing conditions (usually increasing formamide/ urea concentrations) (Anon-2013), means separation of PCR amplicons of the same size but different sequences. This is because these fragments can be separated in a denaturing gradient gel based on their differential denaturation (melting) profiles. It is especially suitable for samples with few species and gives complementary information on species diversity when combined with other methods. It is also well suited for analyzing community changes over time.

In DGGE gel, doublestrand DNA fragments are subjected to an increasing denaturing environment as they encounter increasing concentrations of the denaturing agents (urea or formamide) and partially melt in discrete regions called "melting domains". The melting temperature (T_m) of these domains is sequence-specific. Once the T_m of the lowest melting domain is reached, that part of the fragment becomes partially melted, creating branched "breaking" molecules. This behavior reduces the DNA mobility in the acrylamide gel. Therefore, DNA fragments of the same size but different base pair compositions will show a different response to the denaturing gradient. The different sequences of the DNA fragments will have melting domains with different T_m values that will run different distances in the DGGE (for a detailed description see Roelfsema and Peters 2005).

In practice The DGGE technique exploits (among other factors) the difference in the stability of G-C pairing (3 hydrogen bonds per pairing) as opposed to A-T pairing (2 hydrogen bonds). A mixture of DNA fragments of different sequence is separated by electrophoresis on an acrylamide gel containing a linearly increasing gradient of DNA denaturants (usually urea and formamide). In general, DNA fragments richer in GC will be more stable and remain double-stranded until reaching higher denaturant concentrations. Double-stranded DNA fragments migrate better in the acrylamide gel, while denatured DNA molecules slow down or stop in the gel. In this manner, DNA fragments of differing sequence can be separated in an acrylamide gel. DGGE is commonly performed for partial 16S rRNA gene, but also functional genes may be used. A GC (guanine plus cytosine) rich sequence can be incorporated into one of the primers used in the PCR to modify the melting behaviour of the fragment of interest and to improve the separation of the fragments. The DGGE gels can be stained with DNA

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binding fluorescent dyes, such as SYBR Green and visualized under UV light. Known standards may be used for comparing the samples on different gels. Ideally one band on the gel corresponds to one species, and therefore the number of bands gives an idea of the diversity of the sample.

This method has been chiefly used in several fields of microbial ecology (Ercolini 2004); yet, rarely for fish species identification (Teletchea. 2009). Comi *et al.* (2005) provided a rare example of a comparison between three different PCR methods (RFLP, SSCP and DGGE) used to differentiate eight species commonly used in the production of cod-fish. They found that while RFLP and SSCP were not able to identify all the species tested, DGGE achieved better results. They also found that, in some cases, samples (differing by only one base) belonging to the same species (e.g., cod) migrated in different positions in the gel, illustrating the discriminatory power of DGGE (similar results described by Deagle *et al.* 2005) (Teletchea. 2009).

Karyotyping

Karyotyping is a standard chart of chromosomes isolated from a cell at metaphase arranged in order by size and structure of physical landmark. The study of whole sets of chromosomes is sometimes known as *karyology*.

Karyotypes describe the number of chromosomes, and what they look like under a light microscope. Attention is paid to their length, the position of the centromeres, banding pattern, any differences between the sex chromosomes, and any other physical characteristics. The preparation and study of karyotypes is a part of cytogenetics.

In this technique cells of a species of interest is used for tissue culture, pretreating the cells in a hypotonic solution, which swells them and spreads the chromosomes. Arresting mitosis in metaphase by a solution of colchicine and squashing this preparation on the slide forcing the chromosomes into a single plane. The chromosomes are depicted (by rearranging a microphotograph) in a standard format known as a karyogram or idiogram: in pairs, ordered by size and position of centromere for chromosomes of the same size.

The study of karyotypes is important for cell biology and genetics, and the results may be used in evolutionary biology and medicine. Karyotypes can be used for many purposes; such as, to study chromosomal aberrations, cellular function, taxonomic relationships, and to gather information about past evolutionary events.

Being a basal group in the vertebrate series, fishes possess very old evolutionary history and also expected to yield a good karyotypic variety that should shed some light on their evolutionary relationship. Many taxa shows uniformity in their $2n$ values, whereas many orders and families present karyotypes, though they differ greatly in their evolutionary histories (e.g Acipenserids, Leuscines, Cyprinids, Anguillids, Poecillids and the Perciform groups). On the contrary, several fish groups have highly diverse karyotypes (e.g Esocoids, Salmonids, Cyprinodontids, Oryziatids, Goodeids etc.) (Reddy *et al.*, 2005).

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DNA barcoding

DNA barcoding is a growing concept from 2003, used to screen the large-scale genes, assign unknown individuals and discovery of new species. DNA barcoding works under the principle that inter-species variations are greater than the intraspecies variations (Hebert *et al.*, 2003) allowing one to distinguish the species using nucleotide sequences. Six-fifty nucleotide bases of 5' cytochrome *c* oxidase subunit I gene (COI) have been accepted as a universal barcode to delineate animal life of this planet. At best, single-gene assays can hope to identify an individual to species or reveal inconsistencies between molecular variation and current perceptions of species boundaries. The barcode sequence from each unknown specimen is compared with a library of reference barcode sequences derived from individuals of known identity. Barcoding projects typically involve gathering specimens of a given taxonomic group (identified by conventional taxonomic methods such as morphology), cataloging them together with collateral data such as photographs and locality information, and assembling the barcode library (i.e. a 650-base segment of the COI gene) (Hajibabaei *et al.*, 2005). A specimen is identified if its sequence closely matches one in the barcode library. Otherwise, the new record can lead to a novel barcode sequence for a given species (i.e. a new haplotype or geographical variant), or it can suggest the existence of a newly encountered species. The analysis of DNA barcoding data is usually performed by a clustering method, such as distance-based neighbor-joining (NJ) (Saitou and Nei, 1987), and by evaluating genetic distances within and between species (Hajibabaei *et al.*, 2006).

The protocol of DNA barcoding is simple and less time consuming. DNA can be extracted from the fin clips or muscle tissue by the standard Proteinase-K/Phenol–Chloroform– ethanol method (Sambrook *et al.*, 1989). The concentration of DNA will be estimated using a UV spectrophotometer. The COI gene approximately 650 bp lengths located in the mitochondrial genome will amplify using two sets of primers;
(FishF1–5' TCAACCAACCACAAAGACATTGGCAC 3'
FishR1–5' TAGACTTCTGGGTGGCCAAAGAATCA 3') (Ward *et al.*, 2005).

The homology between the nucleotides and the amino acid sequences will be checked to the known sequences from the genebank using BLAST programmes for the respective sequences (Altschul *et al.*, 1997) of the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI, USA). The sequence analysis is done using different bioinformatics softwares.

In phylogenetic studies, DNA barcoding can be a starting point for optimal selection of taxa, and barcode sequences can be added to the sequence dataset for phylogenetic analysis. In population genetics investigations, DNA barcodes can provide a first signal of the extent and nature of population divergences and will facilitate comparative studies of population diversity in many species. The International Nucleotide Sequence Database (INSDB: GenBank, EMBL, and DDBJ) has adopted a unique keyword identifier (BARCODE) to recognise standard barcode sequences specified by the scientific community.

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Figure showing position of DNA barcode data relative to both population genetics and phylogenetics data. Each small square represents an individual. Different colors are used to represent different species and within-species variation is shown by varying shades of color.

Identification of several fish species using barcoding approach has been reported by many investigators. Australian marine fish species were sequenced for a 655 bp region of mitochondrial COI gene by Ward *et al.*, (2005). The complete mitochondrial genome of the bullhead torrent catfish was sequenced by Kartavtsev *et al.*, (2007). Mitochondrial DNA of the Yellowfin seabream was completely sequenced and a genomic comparison was done among closely related species (Xia *et al.*, 2008). Identification of Canadian fresh water fishes through DNA barcode was reported by Hebert *et al.*, (2008). Analysis of the cytochrome c oxidase 1 gene sequence in six flatfish species (Pleuronectidae) of far-east Russia with inferences in phylogeny and taxonomy was reported Kartavtsev *et al.* (2008). Ward *et al.*, (2008) campaigned for DNA barcoding all fishes and need for establishing and strengthening Fish Barcoding of Life initiative (FISH-BOL). The ability of DNA barcoding to reliably identify the seven commercially important salmon and trout species was reported by Ramussen *et al.*, (2009). Steinke *et al.*, (2009) worked on the DNA based identification for the import of ornamental fish in to North America. The Northern blue-fin tuna was barcoded using COI, as per requirement by Convention on International Trade Endangered Species (CITES) (Lowenstein *et al.*, 2009). Reports of about 41771 fishes, representing 6566 fish species are available on the Barcode of Life Data System; BOLD (Ratnasingham and Hebert, 2007). Krishna *et al.* (2012) worked on the identification of selected estuarine Fishes by DNA Barcoding from River Krishna Region, Andhra Pradesh, India. Sachithanandam *et al.* (2012) worked on the phylogenetic study of Epinephelus species in Andaman coastal region. Description and DNA Barcoding of a New *Sillago* Species, *Sillago sinica* (Family Sillaginidae), from Coastal Waters of China has been done by Tian *et al.* (2011). Coral reef fish larvae were also identified through DNA barcoding (Hebert *et al.*, 2010).

CONCLUSION

Molecular characterization can play a role in uncovering the history, and estimating the diversity, distinctiveness and population structure. Awareness of the level of genetic diversity and the proper management of genetic resources are important issues in modern scenario. New markers deriving from DNA technologies are valuable tools to study genetic variability for conservation purposes. In the near future, the advent of genomics will give an impressive tool for genetic resources evaluation. DNA based methods are mostly applied in the field of taxonomy, forensic examination of food products, food poisoning and genetically modified organisms (GMO) and ecological studies mainly for the determination of early life history stage and trophic relationships. Retrieval

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of DNA sequences from museum specimens and archeological finds and fossil remains are the major problem faced by most of the DNA based methods. The quality and quantity of the DNA will vary greatly; in unprocessed food products DNA is generally unaltered and present in high quality. However, in processed food products DNA is degraded and present in small quantities that inconsiderably reduce the number of DNA fragments with suitable size for molecular analyses.

For avoiding the problems faced by each methods, thorough analyses should be made each time a new group is to be studied (ideally with taxonomists of each group) and several samples from the full distribution range should be taken in to consideration to validate the methods of identification.

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